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**FALSAFA VA HAYOT
XALQARO JURNAL**

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BILIM VA FAOLIYAT DIALEKTIKASINI TA‘MINLASHNING METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI

Annotatsiya. Bilim va faoliyatning dialektikasi – bu insoniyat taraqqiyoti va rivojlanishi uchun muhim jarayon bo‘lib, ularning o‘zaro bog‘liqligi va bir-birini to‘ldirishini tushuntirishga xizmat qiladi. Ushbu maqolada bilim va faoliyat dialektikasini ta‘minlashning metodologik asoslari tahlil qilinadi. Bilim insoniyatning intellektual rivojlanishi va jamiyat taraqqiyoti uchun asosiy omil hisoblanadi. U fan, texnologiya, madaniyat va ijtimoiy hayotning turli sohalarida muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Bilim orqali insonlar tabiat va jamiyat haqidagi tushunchalarini kengaytiradi, muammolarni hal qilish uchun yangi yo‘llar topadi va yangi innovatsiyalar yaratiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: bilim, fan, faoliyat, falsafa, yangi bilim, dialektika metodologiya, innovatsiya, innovatsion yondashuv, intellektual rivojlanish, ijtimoiy taraqqiyot, tadqiqot, tajriba va ko‘nikmalar.

МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ДИАЛЕКТИКИ ПОЗНАНИЯ И ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ

Аннотация. Взаимодействие между знаниями и деятельностью имеет решающее значение для человеческого прогресса и развития, подчеркивая их взаимную зависимость и взаимодополняемость. В данной статье рассматриваются методологические основы, необходимые для поддержания этих диалектических отношений. Знания являются основной движущей силой интеллектуального роста человека и общественного прогресса. Это существенно влияет на различные области, такие как наука, технология, культура и общественная жизнь. Посредством приобретения и применения знаний люди улучшают свое понимание мира природы и общества, разрабатывают инновационные решения проблем и способствуют новым изобретениям.

Ключевые слова: знание, наука, деятельность, философия, новые знания, диалектическая методология, инновация, инновационный подход,

интеллектуальное развитие, социальное развитие, исследования, опыт, навыки.

METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF PROVIDING THE DIALECTIC OF KNOWLEDGE AND ACTIVITY

Annotation. The interplay between knowledge and activity is crucial for human progress and development, highlighting their mutual dependence and complementarity. This article examines the methodological underpinnings necessary to maintain this dialectic relationship. Knowledge is a primary driver of human intellectual growth and societal advancement. It significantly impacts various fields such as science, technology, culture, and social life. Through the acquisition and application of knowledge, individuals enhance their understanding of the natural world and society, devise innovative solutions to challenges, and foster new inventions.

Key words: knowledge, science, activity, philosophy, new knowledge, dialectic methodology, innovation, innovative approach, intellectual development, social development, research, experience, and skills.

INTRODUCTION

The dialectic of knowledge and action refers to the profound interrelationship between our understanding of the world and our relationship to it. These dynamic relationships are fundamental to human progress, shaping our views, actions, and the evolution of societies. We should note that in the development of philosophical thinking, the complex interdependence of knowledge and activity, how they complement each other, the questioning of the dialectic of knowledge and activity, and debates about complementarity have arisen. The basis of the methodological foundations of ensuring the dialectic of knowledge and activity with philosophical knowledge serves the formation of new pragmatic approaches.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

"Philosophy has many methodological approaches and includes formational, civilization-technological, socio-cultural and other paradigms in the study of society and its spheres of life. Each of them solves cognitive problems in its own way, complementary tasks, covering the whole society and its various spheres. Based on this, it is appropriate to analyze the formation, civilization-technological and socio-cultural approaches, and give their main ones. characteristics and relationships with each other, and on this basis, it makes it possible to form the foundations of the methodology of holistic analysis of society and to study social phenomena". [Teoriya i metodologiya nauchnogo issledovaniya, 2017. - С. 131].

DISCUSSION AND THE RESULTS

Knowledge is the basis of human activity. Acquiring knowledge is a continuous process involving learning, while action involves achieving practical

results. Knowledge involves the accumulation of information, concepts, and insights gained through various means such as education, experience, and observation. Knowledge empowers people and societies by providing them with the tools to understand the complexity of the world around them. It is through knowledge that we make sense of our past, analyze our present, and envision a potential future. In addition, knowledge fuels innovation, driving advances in science, technology, culture, and all aspects of human activity. However, knowledge itself does not find its reflection in the life of individuals and society at a high level without activity. It is the knowledge acquired through activity - action, experience, and practical skills - that becomes relevant and serves to achieve the intended goal. Activity transforms abstract ideas into concrete results, and bridges the gap between theory and practice. It achieves progress that moves individuals and societies forward by turning aspirations into achievements. Whether through scientific inquiry, artistic expression, social activism, or economic entrepreneurship, activity is the catalyst that turns the transformative potential of knowledge into reality.

Knowledge provides the theoretical basis, and activity involves the practical application of this knowledge. For example, in the field of medicine, doctors acquire knowledge through years of study and research (theory), but it is their clinical practice (activity) that allows them to diagnose and effectively treat patients. Knowledge serves to form innovations by creating new ideas, concepts and technologies. Activities then involve implementing these innovations, testing their viability, and refining them based on real-world feedback.

Knowledge encourages critical thinking and reasoning, which leads to informed decision-making. Action transforms these decisions into actions, shaping individual behavior and social outcomes. As knowledge expands and evolves, so must our activities and approaches. The dialectic between knowledge and action promotes adaptation to new challenges, resilience and progress. Furthermore, the dialectic of knowledge and action is not a linear process, but rather a dynamic and iterative process. It involves continuous feedback loops in which activity informs knowledge by revealing new ideas and problems, and knowledge, in turn, guides and reinforces future activity. Similarly, the dialectic of knowledge and activity plays a decisive role in social conditions. We can separately analyze the dialectical (continuous education), integrative (interdisciplinary cooperation), epistemological (evidence-based practice) and pragmatic (introduction of innovation) methodological foundations of the reliability of knowledge and its reflection in activity.

The organization of continuing education serves as a basis for the acquisition of initial fundamental knowledge. This, in turn, requires the introduction of the cluster system in the educational process. "The cluster system of pedagogical education development operates in the general areas related to teaching, creating educational literature, increasing the scientific potential of pedagogic personnel, and the integration of education and training. At the moment, these general directions are being privatized in directions such as management and organization

of education, ensuring coherence and integration between types and directions of education, using teaching methods and tools". [Sobirov.B 2021. 1522 p.]. Of course, the interaction between theory and practice is important in various fields, including the educational system. This knowledge is acquired through formal education, scientific research, clinical research and continuing professional development.

Education professionals engage in continuous learning and professional development to stay abreast of the latest advances in science-based knowledge and technology. This continuing education enhances their theoretical understanding and improves their practical skills, ultimately benefiting their careers. Also, the introduction of philosophical education into the continuous education process serves for the integration of science and society. At present, teaching of philosophy has been introduced in the higher education system of most countries of the world. Philosophical education represents a specific form of philosophical activity in the field of education. The very concept of education needs to be clarified. The goal of such philosophical activity is to perceive a more perfect view of education, as well as its development, interpretation, and wide application in practice at all social levels. In the process of such a philosophical analysis, the category of "education" itself is understood as a process of constant development and renewal. [Kuznetsova A.Ya. 2010. – #1. - S.56-57]. After all, "philosophy is usually called the reflection of the times in thoughts, the spiritual quintessence of its time". [Shermukhamedova. N.A. B-73]. Philosophy plays an important role in the study of deep, comprehensive reflection on world events and serves the understanding of social reality.

Ensuring interdisciplinary cooperation serves as a basis for ensuring the objectivity of knowledge. These collaborations facilitate the sharing of knowledge, experiences, and perspectives, which serve to provide comprehensive support to each discipline and to build interdisciplinary consensus. While theoretical knowledge provides a foundational understanding, through practice and continuous learning, professionals in each field achieve evidence-based knowledge, and the results contribute to the development of the philosophy of science. "The new paradigm became the basis for mutual understanding between supporters of different approaches to history and views on the purpose and scientific tasks of philosophical and historical research. This, in turn, increased interest in consensus as a socio-cultural principle of the historical process". [Sizemskaya.I.N. 2022. T. 4. No. 1. S. 69–79]. Basically, the dialectic between theory and practice in science emphasizes the importance of a comprehensive approach to professional activity.

Evidence-based practice represents a paradigm shift in a variety of fields, including health, education, social work, and management. This requires a systematic approach that integrates the best available evidence based on research, universal values, to improve decision-making and outcomes. From a philosophical perspective, answers are sought to fundamental questions about knowledge, ethics, and evidence itself. At the heart of evidence-based practice is the concept of knowledge and its acquisition. Empirical evidence derived from rigorous research

methodology is preferred over the cumulative method. This shift reflects a commitment to scientific inquiry, critical thinking, and continuous improvement of knowledge. At the same time, it raises questions about the limitations of evidence, the role of intuition and tacit knowledge, and the interpretation of conflicting data. Philosophers of science, on the other hand, promote methodological rigor, reproducibility, and the achievement of new knowledge in the creation of reliable evidence. Yet the complexity of human experience and contexts often makes it difficult to apply rigorous scientific criteria to all situations. Proponents of evidence-based practice argue for understanding the use of qualitative research and a variety of sources in acquiring experiential knowledge alongside quantitative data. Ethical considerations also come to the fore in the philosophical analysis of evidence-based practice. It underpins the principle of beneficence, which emphasizes doing good and maximizing benefits for individuals and society. Ethical dilemmas arise when evidence-based guidelines conflict with preferences, cultural values, or resource limitations. Challenges in implementing evidence-based practice also require philosophical considerations. These challenges include barriers to translation of research into practice, resistance to change, bias in the interpretation of evidence, and limitations of existing evidence synthesis methods. Philosophers and practitioners collaborate to address these challenges through interdisciplinary dialogue, methodological innovation, critical appraisal skills, and continuous quality improvement in evidence synthesis processes. Philosophical analysis of evidence-based practice reveals its complexities, nuances, and implications for knowledge, ethics, and social values. Represents a commitment to ethical decision-making and continuous learning. Philosophical inquiry is enriched by engaging with questions such as epistemology, ethics, and the evolving nature of evidence in different contexts. Embracing this interdisciplinary dialogue fosters a more robust, reflective and ethically informed approach to evidence-based practice across disciplines.

Innovation and implementation form a dynamic cycle of change that drives progress in a variety of fields, from technology and science to business and social change. Philosophically, this cycle raises profound questions about creativity, knowledge, ethics, and the impact of innovation on individuals and societies. "Philosophical knowledge forms the methodological basis of education, that is, it plays an important role in scientific research, design, and methodical and innovative organization of the educational process in pedagogical activity. It is these philosophical inquiries that lead to the adoption of systematic, activity-based, cultural, and value-based preferences in education, leading to the development of the field of education. Views on the philosophical understanding of education help to clarify the role and position of the network in society, to identify important features aimed at eliminating unstable, conflicting and problematic situations in the system". [Alibekov D. 2020. Pp. 212-215].

At the heart of innovation lies human creativity, the ability to create new ideas, concepts and technologies that expand the boundaries of attainable knowledge. Philosophically, innovation reflects the human ability to imagine,

solve problems, and imagine alternative futures. Philosophers have long pondered the nature of creativity, discussing its sources, processes, and ethical issues. Implementation involves turning innovative ideas into practical applications, testing their viability, and refining them based on real-life feedback. This process requires collaboration, resource allocation, risk assessment, and adaptation to changing contexts. Philosophical research in implementation examines responsibility, accountability, and the ethical implications of introducing new technologies or practices into society. It considers factors such as unintended consequences, equity in use, environmental impact and long-term sustainability.

Innovation requires a departure from traditional thinking, a change in dogmatic standards, and a change from novelty to progress. Knowledge plays a central role in stimulating innovation. ["Teoriya i metodologiya nauchnogo issledovaniya". 2017, page 131]. It includes not only existing knowledge and experience, but also curiosity, inquiry, and a willingness to question assumptions. Philosophers of science and technology examine how knowledge is produced, validated, and disseminated in innovation systems. Implementation involves turning innovative ideas into practical applications, testing their viability, and refining them based on real-life feedback. This process requires collaboration, resource allocation, risk assessment, and adaptation to changing contexts. Philosophical research in implementation examines responsibility, accountability, and the ethical implications of introducing new technologies or practices into society. It considers factors such as unintended consequences, equity in use, environmental impact and long-term sustainability.

CONCLUSION

The interplay between knowledge and activity is central to development across various domains. Ensuring this dialectical thinking through the adoption of methodological principles from systems approaches, and theoretical advancements in the relationship between the individual and society, can lead to effective practical applications, while practical experiences continually enhance theoretical understanding. This dynamic interaction is crucial for fostering innovation, solving complex problems, and ensuring sustainable development in an ever-changing world. The dialectic of knowledge and activity symbolizes the dynamic relationship that underpins human development. Knowledge provides the intellectual foundation, while activity enables practical application and implementation. Embracing this dialectic involves cultivating a culture that values continuous learning, critical thinking, experimentation, and action. By acknowledging and leveraging this interaction, individuals and societies can navigate complexities, solve problems, and advance towards a more promising and productive future.

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